

FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN ENSURING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION**Kazimova M.Nafisakhan****docent of Kokand State Pedagogical Institute, Uzbekistan****Abdumannonova Rayhon Avaz qizi****Student of KSPI, Uzbekistan**

Annotation: In this article, the work carried out in the educational process, attention to the quality of education, work carried out as education in foreign countries, opinions and works of scientists about the quality of education, information about the quality of education about the increase is provided.

Key words: quality of education, education system, modern technologies, Japanese methods, Japanese innovative management methods, European and American methods.

Enter. The results of the study of the features of the educational system in developed foreign countries and the analysis of the achievements in this field allowed us to determine the following: the determination of the content of education on the basis of a social order serves as a foundation for the comprehensive development of society. This creates conditions for a person's embodied development and manifestation of his potential.[1]

The quality of education is the level of development of education as a state-state system (including any educational institution) and its place in the international rating of education systems. It is determined by the commonality and correlation between the features of the system itself and the "pedagogical product", i.e. its alumni. The quality of the system is its financial, economic, legal, material-technical, organizational, pedagogical, methodological, informational, psychological-pedagogical provision. Characteristics of "pedagogical product" - useful personal characteristics acquired and developed by people in the educational system, contributing to the moral and material well-being of a person in society. "Good" education makes a person competitive in the labor market, helps to establish a harmonious relationship with society and contributes to its formation. a healthy lifestyle provides the spiritual and cultural foundations of life, personal life.

Today, the quality of education is determined by a number of indicators: the purpose of the education system and its satisfaction of the educational needs of people; reliability (stability of results), ergonomics (maintenance of hygienic and anthropometric standards); aesthetics, manufacturability, regulatory accuracy, etc. The quality of education is determined by certification, licensing and accreditation of students and teachers. [1]

Literature analysis

In local literature, there are several main approaches to consider the concept of "educational quality". Thus, M.M. Potashnik considers this to be in accordance with the requirements of educational standards. In this context, the quality of education works as "the ratio of goals and results, measures to achieve rapid and predictable goals in the field of potential development of students." The quality of education V.A. Kachalov and V.D. Shadrikov. How is the compliance of educational services with society's expectations determined by the quality of education M.V. Rizhakov. This reflects the fact that the social dimension is increasingly emphasized in the concept of the formation of competences and skills of future professionals from the point of view of consumers.

Recently, it is important to distinguish between the concepts of quality of education received and quality of education provided, as well as to justify a holistic view of all the diversity of education quality.[2]

Another approach allows us to consider the quality of education not only as a result, but as a process with complex development dynamics due to changes in the activity of educational institutions and the individual, as well as changes in society. , the economic, technological and political environment that surrounds them. Then the quality of education should not be limited to the goals and values of the educational institutions, it should fully satisfy the social, economic and cultural needs of the society, increase their contribution to the development of the society and its human potential.

Constantly and every time at a new socio-economic level of society, the problem of developing the entire educational system is urgent, and its main trends are attention to the individual and creation of optimal conditions for his upbringing, development and development. education, standardization of educational content, design of educational system, their management and evaluation of their quality level.[3]

As you can see, the quality of education is a complex indicator:

- * interrelationship of educational goal and result;
- * ensuring the level of satisfaction of educational process participants' expectations from the provided educational services;
- * certain level of knowledge, skills, abilities and qualifications, mental, physical and moral development of a person;

At the same time, it is the system, model, organization and procedures that guarantee the necessary social development of students. From the point of view of modern didactics, the following features of modern quality education are distinguished:

- the conceptual level of the content in accordance with the level of scientific and technical development;
- its interdisciplinary, competence and activity character;
- direction, interests, wishes, opportunities and individual characteristics of students;
- changing, alternative and problematic education with wide use of information technologies;
- creation of different cultural environments for multicultural education with the aim of spiritual enrichment and formation of readiness to live in a multi-ethnic environment;
- the independent feature of the assessment of the results is educational work and the level of personal development;
- providing conditions for self-assessment, self-evaluation and self-management in training and development.[4]

The result of quality education is such abilities (characteristics) of a person: self-organization, including moral; self-transformation activities; self identification. After all, an educated person must be competitive, successful and in demand in the labor market. He should be able to easily and freely adapt to the rapidly changing socio-economic conditions, making good use of the received education. According to J. Delor, a person should master the "three pillars of education": learning to learn, learning to work, learning how to live.

The concept of "quality" entered education from the manufacturing sector, where quality is understood as a set of characteristics that determine the degree of suitability of a product for its intended use. Therefore, in production, certain characteristics are distinguished from the product, and their value is considered from the consumer's position. The list of qualities is based on standards, standards. Quality is not the end result, it is only a means of determining whether a product conforms to a standard.[5,6]

The term "quality" in education was used for the first time in 1975 in normative documents related to the characteristics of the quality of knowledge of students in education, and then in 1977, a laboratory for evaluating the quality of knowledge was created. But until now, a clear definition of the quality of education has not been created.

The concept of quality production cannot be transferred to the field of education, because the consumers of educational services are different categories of the population, and the choice

of qualities and their value are determined by them in different ways. Thus, in the understanding of parents, quality is the development and upbringing of children and their preparation for the next stage of education, in the understanding of students - the creation of favorable learning conditions, in the understanding of teachers - the provision of education. programs, textbooks, process with appropriate equipment, for employers - the necessary qualities and skills, for society as a whole - to create value orientations expressed among students, for example, in a civic position.

- quality of education - quality of education; this interpretation is accepted in educational institutions, where the results are summarized in a numerical format by dividing students into groups and calculated as a percentage of educational results, that is, the percentage of students who completed education without "2" during the reporting period. ", and quality - the percentage of students who completed the reporting period of study with "3", that is, "4" and "5";

- the quality of education - the harmony of the quality of education and training;

- quality of education - level of personal development;

- the quality of education - the percentage of school graduates who entered higher educational institutions and the number of winners of Olympiads of various levels;

- the quality of education - the graduate's readiness for life in 6 positions: readiness for work, defense of the Motherland, family life, rational spending of free time, continuous study, and health care .[6]

In the most authoritative publications, such as the books "Monitoring the quality of education at school" by S. Shishov and V. Kalney, the dictionary-reference "Management in the school" (edited by A. Moiseev) and the manual "Quality of education". "management" (edited by M. Potashnik) means "a social category that determines the state and efficiency of the educational process in society, its compliance with the needs and expectations of the development and formation of society (different social groups). civil, everyday and professional powers of a person.

Conclusion. The quality of education is determined by a set of indicators describing various aspects. Educational activities of the educational institution: content of education, forms and methods of education, material and technical base, provision of personnel, etc., ensure the development of the competences of the young people they study.[7.8]

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